

The Positive and Negative Social Capital

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Social capital can be defined as trust, norms and networks that facilitate cooperation for mutual benefit (Putnam, 1993: 167). However, the concept of social capital is not always positive. This article will discuss positive and negative social capital.

Social capital can be useful when cooperation for mutual benefit can be facilitated by social network and norms of reciprocity (Putnam, 2000: 21). In this context, both individuals and organisations agree to mobilise joint resources to achieve common outcomes which are more efficient and productive. This agreement is built on trustworthiness and by being tolerant about their differences and diversity. For example, rotating credit associations (RCAs), informal groups, which meet periodically, every member contributing a set amount to a common pool and finance will be received by each in turn. Obviously, this system will not work if there is no trust between the members (Portes, 1998: 13). The members benefit because they can access finance without any long procedure of administration and high interest. Furthermore, social capital also contributes to creating social order such as preventing members of the community from having deviant behaviours (Portes, 1998: 10). This is because in tight community networks, parents, teachers and police authorities seek to maintain discipline and promote compliance among those under their charge. As the result, the members with deviant behaviours are easy to identify. This is because when a child is found deviant, such as a boy who joins into a gang or a girl who becomes pregnant without getting married, the neighbours will inform their parents and teachers. Their parents will be ashamed and give more attention to their children. This system leads to harmonising so that by collective sanction people will live peacefully without any fear, since the number of crimes can be eliminated.

On the other hand, social capital can be negative when it brings benefits to group members, but bars others from getting resources (Portes, 1998: 16). For example, an ethnic community may exclude others from using their resources. If this cannot be solved, then it will trigger conflict and disunity. Another negative social capital is when it restricts individual freedom. Berger, in his book 'Pyramids of Sacrifice', gives an example of how a woman from a Mexican village felt confused between two choices of continuing her study and getting a better job, or sends her money to her relatives in her village. This problem happened because the social capital restricted her freedom by strong local norms (Berger, 1974: 217-224). This phenomenon also explains how a group or community creates demands of conformity which can reduce the privacy and autonomy of individuals (Portes, 1998: 16-17). Finally, another negative aspect of social capital occurs when a group or community prefers to live in exclusive areas and prefers not to be in contact with other outsiders. They still keep their norms without knowing modernisation. As a result, their norm will be down graded and isolated. The members live in small community as a consequence of trying to escape from this norm (Portes, 1998: 17).

In conclusion, social capital is like a two-edge sword. If it is not managed well, it may create trouble for the member of the community itself.

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